

CENTRIC RELATION AND ITS DETERMINATION IN FULL MOUTH REHABILITATION : A REVIEW

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Abstract:

Unguided closure is not a valid method to determine the proper maxillo-mandibular relationship, even if centric relation is a commonly utilized physiologic position. The condyles are not always entirely seated in a centric relation when there is an unguided closure cause. The term "convenience position" or "habitual closure" refers to an unguided closure because of its propensity to close toward the maximal intercuspation position. Muscular imbalances resulting from occlusal interference also have a significant impact on unguided closures; therefore, it is important to note that a verified centric relation requires a hands-on treatment. Mandibular manipulation is not intended to press the jaw into a centric position. The condyles are almost always positioned incorrectly when the jaw is forced. The chin point guidance approach tends to force the condyles down and back by pushing the jaw back.

Introduction:

Nowadays, prosthodontists have a lot more options when it comes to diagnosing, planning, and treating patients in their clinical practices when utilizing digital methods. However, we also need to be aware of the fact that physicians are not as focused on carrying out the primary clinical phases of prosthodontic tooth rehabilitation, which might result in errors and further issues following prosthodontic rehabilitation.

One phase, known as the foundational phase, includes identifying the centric relation (CR) of the jaws. Errors in this step can lead to occlusal and muscle dysfunction, causing pain in the

craniomandibular and craniocervical regions. There are various challenges that arise from the interpretation of the CR concept, as well as the indications and contraindications for determining this position, along with the methods used for its recording, some of which are contradictory. Numerous studies have identified over thirty different interpretations of the CR concept and the methods employed to determine it. The most commonly used techniques include bilateral manipulation by P.E. Dawson, CR registration by frontal deprogrammer as proposed by Lucia V. O., and variations such as the leaf gauge by Long J. H., and the intraoral device for recording the Gothic arch angle by Gysi A. Dawson's technique involves manually controlling the mandible's direction and locating the TMJ condyles in their physiological terminal position. This position is then recorded using a special hard wax with the addition of aluminum particles (AluWax by Maarc) for CR registration. The frontal deprogrammer is a bite plate with a flat surface that divides the masticatory group of teeth, allowing for the conversion of lower jaw movements in the transversal plane, while the condyles remain in their terminal position in centric relation.

Definition:

1. Centric relation: \sěn'trīk rǐ-la'shun\; acronym is CR; a maxillomandibular relationship, independent of tooth contact, in which the condyles articulate in the anterior-superior position against the posterior slopes of the articular eminences; in this position, the mandible is restricted to a purely rotary movement; from this unstrained, physiologic, maxillomandibular relationship, the patient can make vertical, lateral or protrusive movements; it is a clinically useful, repeatable reference position.
2. condylar inclination \kǒn'da-lar ǐn'kla-na'shun\; the direction of the condyle path (GPT-4)
3. condylar path \kǒn'da-lar path\; that path traveled by the mandibular condyle in the temporomandibular joint during various mandibular movements
4. condylar path element \kǒn'da-lar path ěl'a-ment\; the member of a dental articulator that controls the direction of condylar movement
5. condylar path tracing \kǒn'da-lar path tra'sǐng\; a graphic registration of the movement of the condyle; syn, MANDIBULAR TRACING
6. condylar guidance \kǒn'da-lar gǐd'ns\ n: the mechanical form located in the posterior region of an articulator that controls movement of its mobile member
7. condylar guide assembly \kǒn'da-lar gǐd a-sēm'ble\; the components of an articulator that guide movement of the condylar analogues
8. condylar guide inclination \kǒn'da-lar gǐd ǐn'kla-na'shun\; the angle formed by the inclination of a condylar guide control surface of an articulator and a specified reference plane; comp,
9. LATERAL CONDYLAR INCLINATION condylar hinge position \kǒn'da-lar hǐnj pā-zǐsh'an\ obs: the position of the condyles of the mandible in the glenoid fossae at which hinge axis movement is possible

DETERMINING CENTRIC RELATION:

Centric relation, although commonly used, is not a reliable method for determining the correct maxillo-mandibular relationship through unguided closure. This is because the condyles may not always be fully seated in centric relation during unguided closure. Instead, unguided closure tends to move towards the maximal intercuspation position, which is why it

is referred to as a "convenience position" or a "habitual closure." Muscle disharmonies resulting from occlusal interference also greatly affect unguided closures. Therefore, it is crucial to use a hands-on technique to ensure a verifiable centric relation. The goal of manipulating the mandible is not to forcefully position the jaw into centric relation, as this often leads to inaccurate condyle positioning. The commonly used method of chin point guidance tends to push the jaw back, forcing the condyles down and back.

DIFFERENT METHODS TO DETERMINE CENTRIC RELATION ARE:

1. Using bilateral manipulation to find and verify centric relation or adapted centric posture
2. Anterior Bite Stops
3. Directly Fabricated Anterior Deprogramming Device
4. The Pankey Jig
5. The Best-bite Appliance
6. The Lucia Jig
7. NTI (Nociceptive Trigeminal Inhibition)
8. Load the Joints
9. Leaf Gauge

1. Using bilateral manipulation to find and verify centric relation or adapted centric posture

Positioning the mandible in centric relation can be achieved through methods other than bilateral manipulation, however have shown that bilateral manipulation is the most consistently accurate and repeatable method for recording centric relation. This conclusion is supported by various university studies as well. The primary reason for utilizing bilateral manipulation is its high level of accuracy.

Why use bilateral manipulation?

The primary objective of bilateral manipulation is to ensure optimal placement of the properly aligned condyle-disk assemblies. In a study conducted by Williamson, the results from laminographic studies were presented, providing evidence in favor of this concept. It becomes evident that achieving a superior position of the condyles is crucial, supporting Dawson's hypothesis of centric relation, which refers to the condyles being positioned superiorly in the glenoid fossae.

Bilateral manipulation offers a convenient means of swiftly verifying three key aspects:

- 1) the accuracy of the position,
- 2) the alignment of the condyle-disk assembly, and
- 3) the integrity of the articular surfaces.

It is fast and uncomplicated.

Procedure :**• Step_one:**

Recline the patient all the way back.

Point the chin up.

A supine patient is more relaxed and in a better position for the operator to work while seated. Pointing the chin up makes it easier to position the fingers on the mandible and prevents the tendency of some patients to protrude the jaw.

• Step_two:

Stabilize the head.

Lower the patient's head enough so you can cradle it between your rib cage and forearm. Some dentists find it more comfortable to position the top of the patient's head in the center of their abdomen.

This has some disadvantages in that there is a tendency to pull back on the mandible. It is also more difficult to see in the mouth from that position and is a bit awkward for the assistant in four-handed procedures.

- **Step three:**
After the head is stabilized, lift the patient's chin again to slightly stretch the neck. Be sure you are comfortably seated, with the patient low enough to allow you to work with your forearm approximately parallel to the floor.

- **Step four:**
Gently position the four fingers of each hand on the lower border of the mandible. The little finger should be slightly behind the angle of the mandible. Position the pads of your fingers so they align with the bone, as if you were going to lift the head. Keep all four fingers tightly together.

- **Step five:**
Bring the thumbs together to form a C with each hand. The thumbs should fit in the notch above the symphysis. No pressure should be applied at this time. All movements should be made gently.

- Step six:
With a very gentle touch, manipulate the jaw so it slowly hinges open and closed. As it hinges, the mandible will usually slip up into centric relation automatically if no pressure is applied. Any pressure applied before the condyles are completely seated will be resisted by the lateral pterygoid muscles. The key at this point is delicacy. There should be no pressure and no jig gling, as this also activates muscle response. Use slow hingeing movements so the muscles are not triggered into contraction.

If the patient resists even gentle manipulation by holding the jaw in protrusion, position the hands gently and then ask the patient to hinge open and close. At the point that closing action starts to occur, the mandible will usually retrude automatically. If the hands simply ride along with the patient's own jaw movement, you will feel the jaw go back. Then hold it firmly on that hinge position in preparation for the next step.

- Step seven:
After the mandible feels like it is hingeing freely and the condyles seem to be fully seated up in their fossae, most experienced clinicians will assume that the mandible is in centric relation.

2. Anterior Bite Stops:

Numerous variations of anterior stops exist, each with their own unique characteristics. These stops prove effective when they allow for the separation of all posterior teeth and when the condyles have unrestricted horizontal and vertical movement to reach their highest seated positions. It is important to note that all of these appliances necessitate the use of a bite material for the posterior teeth once centric relation has been established.

3. Directly Fabricated Anterior Deprogramming Device

The initial fabrication method for anterior deprogramming devices involved directly molding autocuring acrylic resin to fit the upper incisors' incisal edges.

The mandible would be manipulated to achieve centric relation or a close approximation during the pliable stage. Subsequently, the lower incisors would indent the soft acrylic as the jaw closed, but the closure would be halted before reaching posterior contact. Once the curing process was finished, the tooth contact surface would be ground down to create a smooth, flat surface that allowed for complete horizontal movement of the mandible.

Fig: Directly Fabricated Anterior Deprogramming Device

4. The Pankey Jig

The Pankey jig was designed many years ago by Dr. Keith Thornton. It is cost-effective and easy to use. It is fixated on the upper central incisors with autocure acrylic or any hard-setting material. The lower incisors slide freely against a flat surface to give unimpeded freedom for condylar movement to centric relation.

5. The Best-bite Appliance

It works exactly the same way as the Pankey jig. A kit is available with an injection material for stabilizing the appliance. A book by Dr. Jerry Simons can be used for patient education to explain the relationship of occlusal interferences to TMJ pain and headaches.

6. The Lucia Jig

The Lucia jig functions similarly to other anterior stops, as it was one of the earliest devices to incorporate an anterior stop. Initially, Lucia's design was angled to guide the condyles distally, influenced by early misunderstandings about centric relation being in its most

retruded position. However, Dr. Peter Neff later made modifications to the jig, allowing for upward movement of the condyles without causing distalization.

7. NTI (Nociceptive Trigeminal Inhibition)

The NTI device has been heavily advertised as an appliance for treating migraine headaches and other facial pain problems. The functionality of this method is identical to the other techniques mentioned earlier. In cases where the pain in the masticatory system and the headache stem from an occluso-muscle disorder, which is often the case, separating the posterior teeth, properly aligning the TMJs, and relaxing the inferior lateral pterygoid muscles will lead to centric relation and alleviate the pain, including any associated headaches. However, if the pain is primarily caused by an intracapsular disorder, none of the aforementioned devices will fully alleviate the pain or establish a correct centric relation.

8. Leaf Gauge

The leaf gauge, one of the most popular aids for determining centric relation (Figure 9-11), was introduced by Dr. Hart. This apparatus is composed of sheets of pliable mylar that can be modified to different thicknesses. The concept involves creating space between the back teeth by inserting the gauge between the front teeth.

The mylar material is sleek and slippery, enabling the lower jaw to shift horizontally as the condyles align. It serves as a tool for deprogramming to release tension in the lateral pterygoid muscles. Once centric relation is established (verified through load testing), layers of the gauge can be taken out until the initial tooth contact is made.

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